

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Seed treatment against tungro (RTV)

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We evaluated five levels of furathiocarb (Promet 40 SD) for seed treatment against RTV in Maros and Lanrang, South Sulawesi. Seed was submerged 24 h and air-dried 10 min, then mixed with furathiocarb powder. Seeds were planted 24 h after treatment in 2- × 4-m seedbeds.

Green leafhopper (GLH) populations were estimated by covering each hill once a week to 4 wk after sowing (WAS) with a 20- × 20- × 30-cm transparent mylar cage and counting GLH in the cage. Ten cages per seedbed were used with 3 replications.

In Maros, GLH population and RTV

Effect of seed treatment on GLH population and RTV incidence in South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Treatment (g furathiocarb/kg seed)	GLH/hill (WAS)				RTV incidence (%)
	1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	
	<i>Maros</i>				
10	0.2	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.5
15	0.0	0.4	0.6	0.9	0.4
20	0.0	1.2	0.9	0.8	0.2
25	0.2	0.9	0.4	1.4	0.2
40	0.3	1.1	1.2	1.4	0.0
Control	0.1	1.0	1.3	2.0	1.3
	<i>Lanrang</i> ^a				
10	13 abc	25 a	17 ab	13 ab	65
15	17 bc	24 a	17 ab	15 bc	81
20	10 ab	23 a	13 ab	11 ab	77
25	13 abc	24 a	13 a	9 ab	26
40	8 a	22 a	11 a	7 a	20
Control	20 c	32 a	26 b	22 c	88

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level (DMRT).

incidence were low even 7 WAS (see table). Although GLH populations were quite high in Lanrang, RTV infection did not appear until 4 WAS. Incidence

was 20-90% 7 WAS. Furathiocarb at 25 and 40 g/kg seeds provided the best control in Lanrang. □

Heat and chemical therapy to eradicate *Pseudomonas fuscovaginatae* from rice seed

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Seedborne and seed-transmitted fluorescent *Pseudomonas* spp. have been shown to cause sheath rot, and grain discoloration and sterility in Japan, southern Europe, Africa, and Latin America. The pathogens have been identified as *P. syringae* pv. *syringae*, *P. fuscovaginatae* (= *P. marginalis* = *P. fluorescens* biovar II), but the taxonomy is unclear.

National quarantine norms often require that imported seed be free of seed-transmitted pathogens. We undertook studies to evaluate chemical seed treatment and heat therapy for eradicating pathogens from rice seed.

Dry heat is known to eradicate *P. fuscovaginatae* from seed, but the long-term effect on seed viability is not known. Hot water therapy (55°C, 20 min) to eradicate *Aphelenchoides besseyi* from seed is a common practice. Tetracycline is known to reduce *P. fuscovaginatae* infection, but agricultural chemicals registered for rice have not been tested.

Kasugamycin, propineb, captan, mancozeb, edifenphos, tricyclazone, benomyl, and captafol, which are commonly used in Latin America to control grain discoloration and neck blast, were prescreened for ability to limit *in vitro* colony growth of isolates from Latin America, Asia, and Africa. Only kasugamycin showed a significant negative effect on colony growth of *P. fuscovaginatae*, and none had a significant effect on *P. syringae* pv. *syringae* or *P. avenae* (nonfluorescent). Therefore, dry heat and hot water were compared with kasugamycin at 0.2 g ai/kg seed for

their efficiencies in eradicating the pathogens. Test seed was harvested from plants inoculated with Latin American isolates of *P. fuscovaginatae*.

The two heat therapies were completely effective (Table 1). Kasugamycin significantly reduced but did not eradicate the pathogen.

We assessed the effect of dry heat

Table 1. Comparison of heat^a and antibiotic treatments for eradicating *Pseudomonas fuscovaginatae* from rice seed.^b Cali, Colombia, 1987.

Isolate	Contamination (%)	
	Untreated	Kasugamycin at 0.2 g ai/kg seed
BCE-3	33	4.0
BCE-23	31.9	0
532	28	2.9

^aThe heat treatments (65°C for 6 d, or 55°C water for 20 min) produced no contamination. ^bSeed from plants inoculated at booting with pathogenic isolates of *P. fuscovaginatae*. Mean of 2 replications, 100 seeds each. All treatments had significantly lower contamination than the untreated for the 3 isolates.

Table 2. Effect of heat treatment on germination and field emergence of seed of 15 widely grown commercial indica cultivars in Latin America, 1987.^a

Cultivar	Origin	Germination in laboratory (%)				Field emergence (%)								
		Initial ^b		8 mo		Initial		5 mo		8 mo				
		No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 6 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 6 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 6 d			
Anayansi	Panama	91	100	80	83	76	73	73	57	60	52	52	52	48
Araure 2	Venezuela	91	98	81	83	83	65	70	54	53	53	66	52	48
BR-IRGA409	Brazil, Guatemala	95	99	88	82	85	74	71	49	49	49	66	47	48
CICA4	Various countries	92	100	87	83	81	69	76	59	56	52	69	45	47
CICA8	Various countries	93	98	83	82	82	64	68	59	56	46	65	50	50
CICA9	Paraguay, Dominican Republic	93	93	81	79	76	73	66	58	60	50	54	53	49
CR1113	Costa Rica	92	99	85	85	85	72	87	60	59	54	67	57	52
Diwani	Surinam	82	93	81	79	80	63	64	49	50	46	56	50	49
INIAP7	Ecuador	92	93	78	86	80	70	67	52	52	53	51	49	49
INTI	Peru	93	99	78	81	82	74	76	56	61	57	57	59	49
JUMA50	Dominican Republic	93	99	85	83	81	83	72	54	54	56	58	53	54
Metica 1	Colombia, Brazil	90	98	87	77	72	79	73	46	54	46	43	51	42
Oryzica 1	Various countries	88	93	79	84	74	66	65	63	49	45	57	45	45
Sinaloa A80	Mexico	95	100	86	87	86	80	73	65	59	54	65	54	52
Tikal 2	Guatemala	93	91	76	86	82	75	72	55	58	48	42	50	45
Mean		91.5	97.2	82.3	82.7	80.3	71.5	71.2	68.5	54.8	55.3	50.7	53.8	48.5

^aAnalysis of variance^c

F (treatment) df = 3

F (variety) df = 15

F (treatment × variety)

Error mean square

ns = not significant, * = significant at P = 0.05, ** = significant at P = 0.01, *** = significant at P = 0.001.

^bAll cultivars had 100% germination under both heat treatments. ^c*** = significant at P = 0.001, ** = significant at P = 0.01, * = significant at P = 0.05, ns = not significant.

Sheath blight diseases in tropical ricefields

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The several kinds of sheath diseases of rice, usually caused by fungus pathogens, produce different types of sclerotia. Their pathogenicity and occurrence have been reported in Japan, China, America, and other places, but little is known about their distribution, frequency, and significance in tropical rice-growing areas. We surveyed their distribution patterns in relation to rice sheath disease incidence in 1985.

Sclerotia extracted from soil samples from several fields were examined under a dissecting microscope. They were identified by size, shape, and color. Distribution frequencies were calculated.

Pure cultures of fungal sclerotia isolated were grown on potato dextrose

therapy (65 °C, 6 d) on the viability of seed of 15 commonly grown Latin American rice varieties. Germination (in petri plates) and field emergence of seed kept at 65 °C for 6 d were compared with those of seed kept at 55 °C for 3 d to break dormancy and with untreated seed. Readings were taken immediately after treatment (1 mo after harvest) and after 5 and 8 mo of post-treatment storage at room temperature. Because hot water therapy has little effect on germination and viability in most varieties, it was not included in the viability studies.

Even after 8 mo of room storage, the treatments differed little in germination, most being around 80% (Table 2). The slight negative effect on field emergence was not enough to prevent a good stand.

The choice of seed treatment depends on the *Pseudomonas* species involved, available facilities; quantity of seed to be treated, and its destination or use. For seed for international exchange and for genetic or basic seed, heat treatment is relatively easy. For commercial certified seed, treatment with kasugamycin could greatly reduce contamination with *P. fuscovaginae* and offer some protection against leaf blast in the seedling stage. □